

SYNTACTICAL DIRECTNESS OF APHORISMS IN ENGLISH

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Abstract. In this research we try to express on the one hand profound interest in learning the syntactic peculiarities of aphorisms in discourse, on the other hand it gives a detailed analysis of the semantic features of them in discourse in English and Uzbek.

Keywords: aphorism, special factors, depository, notions of time, spatial relationships

In Uzbekistan, English has long been regarded as a tool of international communication, and together with its rising importance, the need of learning English is becoming more and more urgent. It cannot be denied that all foreign learners in general and Uzbek learners in particular desire to master English as the native speakers; however, they usually face a lot of difficulties that prevent them from gaining successful conversations. One of the reasons for these problems lies in the way people perceive and use aphorisms. Aphorisms are considered to be special factors of a language's vocabulary system because they reflect cultural special characteristics of each nation, including material and spiritual values. A lot of researchers, therefore, have long shown their interests in aphorisms. Aphorisms are used to express ideas in figurative styles. They bring the vividness and richness to the speaker's speeches; therefore, knowing how to use aphorisms effectively in the right situations becomes essential.

It is really interesting to realize that there are a large number of aphorisms in both English and Uzbek expressing gain and loss in humans' life. Therefore, they have become a linguistic phenomenon that linguistic researchers cannot ignore.

Furthermore, in order to achieve the effective intercultural communicative purpose in the globalization age, we ourselves should be equipped with background knowledge of culture which is known as –the depository of knowledge, experience, beliefs, values, attitudes, meanings, social hierarchies, religion, notions of time, roles, spatial relationships, concepts of the universe and material objects and possessions acquired by a group of people in the course of generations.”¹ Obviously, studying aphorisms of a nation, especially aphorisms related to gain and loss is one of best ways to understand culture as well as people in that nation.

From the reasons mentioned above, the thesis – A Study of Linguistic Features of Aphorisms in English is expected to be an interesting and helpful material for foreign language teachers and learners and for people who are interested in aphorisms in both English and Uzbek.

There have been a lot of researchers conducting investigations into aphorisms in both English and Uzbek. For English aphorisms, the large number of scholars including Taylor, Ridout and Whiting, Norrick, Collis, Galperin and so on has made great contribution to this field. However, based on different approaches and goals, their publications focus on one or another aspect of aphorisms.

Generally, these linguists provide us with an overall picture of theoretical background of how to examine language in use. In view of Uzbek aphorism studies, some elaborate works connected with aphorisms have contributed to the knowledge of the field and one of the wholehearted authors where the difference between idioms and aphorisms is mentioned based on two criteria: content and grammatical structures, the authors collected and compiled some common English aphorisms and the Uzbek equivalents, and these materials helped me a great deal in this study.

In addition, there have been so far some master theses in English on aphorisms carried out by many Uzbek people. After examining the studies mentioned above, it

¹ “What is the importance of using aphorism in our speech?” I Акрамов – Центр научных публикаций (buxdu. uz), 2021.

could be seen that hardly a research into the linguistic features of aphorisms relating to gain and loss in English versus Uzbek has been so far carried out.

In this chapter, we are primarily concerned with Research Methods, Sampling, Data Collection, Data Analysis, Instrumentation. The procedures of performing the research are also presented at the same time. The validity and reliability will be stated and justified at the end of this chapter Generally, Aphorism under study in both English and Uzbek are constructed in simple, compound, complex and comparative sentences.

Concerning complex sentences, both English and Uzbek Aphorism are found to have the second place of percentage. In terms of comparative sentences, both English and Uzbek Aphorism are found to have lowest percentage. Relating to the data of both English and Uzbek comparative sentences, differentiating comparison is used more commonly than equational comparison.

Concerning compound sentences, the number of compound Aphorism in English is far less than that of compound Aphorism in Uzbek. Moreover, English compound Aphorism in form of syndetic coordination are more aphorisms than in form of a syndetic coordination while only compound sentences without coordinators are found in Uzbek samples with 98 aphorisms at 100 % and no Uzbek Aphorism are formed in compound sentences with coordinators.

Relating to the data of complex sentences, English Aphorism are more than Uzbek ones. In addition, English Aphorism are structured in all three kinds of clauses: adjective, nominal and adverbial clauses while Uzbek Aphorism are formed in two kinds: nominal clauses (S-P functioning as sentential elements) and adverbial clauses (S-P functioning as subordinate clauses). As for comparative sentences, the number of comparative Aphorism in English is nearly two times as many as Uzbek ones. From the differences mentioned above, it is easy to recognize that the culture of each country has an effect on their languages.

Meanwhile Uzbek people would like to use coordinators to connect members of sentences, English people would like to express simply and shortly their thoughts and ideas.

It can be clearly seen that both English and Uzbek own a large number of Aphorism in their national treasure of folklore. These aphorisms, in some way, not only provide us with a valuable bag of wisdom but also broaden our awareness of cultural value and life experience. Moreover, one of the most characteristic properties of Aphorism in the two languages is also marked by the use of many similar stylistic devices such as metaphor, antithesis, hyperbole and simile. Thanks to these powerful expressive means, we can create aphorisms with subtle nuances of meaning that no other means can attain. This also proves a fact that English as well as Uzbek like to use figurative image to make their speech more persuasive.

With regard to semantic of Aphorism in English and Uzbek, one can easily realize the phenomenon of the twofold application of meaning in most aphorisms: the surface meaning of the aphorisms and their figurative meaning embodied through the stylistic markers, just mentioned above. In addition, it must be noted that English and Uzbek people meet each other in thought in spite of the fact that they live far from each other. As a matter of fact, the formation as well as the way they generalize their idea in aphorisms are identical. Another identical feature between E aphorism and V aphorism is that they both share the same semantic fields such as labor and business, life experience, family relationship, social relationship, education, destiny, money, characters and some other fields.

Although both English and Uzbek people like to use stylistic devices in their aphorisms to make their utterance more condensed and colorful, the frequency of these expressive means does not always occur correspondence with each other and the case of metonymy is an instance. We can find some metonymic aphorisms in English. In contrast, there are no cases of metonymic aphorisms in Uzbek. This indicates that the difference is resulted from the habit of language use of each nation. What is more, the differences between E Aphorism and V Aphorism are also

revealed through the dissimilarities between cultural characteristics of the two nations. It is obvious that each country has its own civilization, national tradition, religious belief and life condition. These factors, to some extent, impose on their thought then produce different aphorisms as an inevitable consequence.

Additionally, the semantic field does not have the same numbers of Aphorism in English and in Uzbek. This is because different awareness of people in the two nations leads to the difference in describing objects or phenomenon in the objective world. That explains why the aphorisms of the lexical fields such as social relationship, labor and business and money are used more commonly in Uzbek than these in English.

Aphorisms are prefabricated units. They are usually short, pithy and lapidary. And for the sake of memorability, aphorisms tend to be alliterative. The structure of a aphorism is normally fixed and not easy to break. Another feature in the structure of aphorisms is the frequent use of many types of meaning transference such as metaphor and simile which shows the creativity of former generations as well as their original worldview. Regarding content, aphorisms usually bear advice and moral lessons which have been drawn from the real experience of life of many generations.

Before applying aphorisms in practice, it is of first priority to ascertain what each aphorism means. If a person uses a aphorism in a particular text without realizing its meaning, the expression could be used incorrectly and might cause some misunderstandings. In addition, aphorisms may contain more than one stylistic device and, in such a way, they become more impressive and effective, however, at the same time their meanings are harder to perceive. The same aphorism used in different texts or situations can have more or less varying meanings. Moreover, the inner form of aphorisms affected by the flow of time and historical development, which influenced the appearance of new interpretations and applications in situations differing from the traditionally intended ones.

However, the aphorisms with four words in English Aphorism are less frequently used than the ones in Uzbek. Semantically, there are total of 9 groups semantic fields in both languages categorized. Through the process of scientific research, we have also discovered that most aphorisms contain two simultaneous meaning at the same time: literal meaning and figurative meaning, so we sometimes find it difficult to understand the aphorisms at the first sight. Basically, the figurative meaning or implied meaning of aphorisms is usually conveyed through the expensive means such as metaphor, metonymy, hyperbole, simile, or metaphor.

More interestingly, some Uzbek aphorisms have no equivalence in English or vice versa because of the cultural differences from countries to countries. One example of teaching Aphorism combining all above implications is as follows:

- Step 1: providing learners with kinds of sentences in English which are simple, compound, complex, comparative and aphoristic.
- Step 2: supplying two columns: column A consisting of the first part of aphorisms and column B consisting of the second part of aphorisms.
- Step 3: giving definitions or clues for each aphorism.
- Step 4: asking learners to match one part in column A with another in column B to make a complete aphorism which is correct grammatically and suitable with the definition given before.

From these exercises, learners will more easily remember aphorisms syntactically and semantically. Moreover, teachers can ask learners to find out Uzbek equivalent aphorisms so that they can have a deep insight of aphorisms relating to gain and loss in both languages.

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